

DESCRIPTION OF CHULPAN'S POEMS IN THE PRESS

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Annotation: In this article, a strong representative of Uzbek jadid literature Abdulhamid Suleiman spoke about the collective publications and poems published in the press created during the lifetime of his son Chulpan

Keywords: jadid, poetic collection, scientific-critical text, periodicals, literary heritage. For a full-fledged study of the work of representatives of Jadid literature, as well as for promotion, it will be necessary, first of all, to sum up the literary heritage left by them, as well as to determine the main source of support from them. This process is naturally not easy. Because even earlier we said that the personal archives of these creators have not been preserved, which means that the most reliable text of their works - no manuscripts. For this reason, as the original text of his works, we have no choice but to accept the printed books, newspapers and magazines, texts in various almanacs and collections from the life of the authors. Of course, the texts in these publications cannot be considered an absolute author's manuscript, because neither the traces left by the editor nor, as Abdullah Qadiri said, the "interviews of the musahhihs" were left untouched. This makes it necessary to approach these texts critically from the beginning, of course. Nevertheless, we are obliged to recognize those early editions as the main text and rely on them in reprints from the absence of another. It is known from the above that the nazmite heritage of Chulpan lies scattered in turfa sources, and in recent years, efforts to collect the poet's poems in a single publishing source (polyhedra) have also not yet led to the expected result.

The sources from which Chulpan Nazmi heritage occurs can be classified as follows:

- 1) poetic collections that the poet himself ordered;
- 2) community collections, almanacs, textbooks published at the time of life;
- 2) timed press releases;
- 3) various sources (memoirs, works of others, etc.).

In this article, we draw on the analysis of collective collections, almanacs, textbooks and poems from timed press publications published during the time of life of Chulpan. Even in this type of source, many poems of the poet, variants of poetry and other examples of creativity have reached us.

The collective collection "Uzbek young poets" was published by Turkestan state publishing house in 1922 [1. 25-60]. The collection samples poems by Fitrat, Chulpan, Botu and Elbek, promising young poets of Uzbek literature of the time. 14 poems of Chulpan placed from it ("In times of love", "Beautiful", "Khayali", "Zarafshan", "Kalandar love", "To nature, "Sleep", "When Baku goes to the east Congress", "Excerpt", "To the light star", "Purtana", "Dawn of controversy" "Oriental light", "For the Uzbek daughter"). The contents are also evident in the fact that the collection included a number of artistically poignant, now well-known poems by

Chulpan. It is this collection that can also be said that Chulpan was first known to readers for all his height as a poet.

From the copies of the collection are kept in the following places: in the Institute of Oriental Studies named after Abu Rayhon Beruniy (№12832-II L, №12140 L), in the Memorial Museum of the memory of the victims of repression, in the Istanbul Atatürk library of Turkey (№193), there are also xeronuskhas taken from the original in the Chulpan Memorial sections of the State Museum of Literature named after Alisher Navoi and the State Museum of history and culture of Andijan region.

The compilers of the complex named "Fragments of literature" were Abdulhamid Sulayman and Ashurali Zohiri, which was published by the Uzbek state publishing house in 1926. In parentheses on the title sheet of the complex is the comment for students, teachers and literature lovers in general [2. 3]. From this it becomes known that the complex is planned as educational literature. The collection gives a total of 20 poems by Chulpan, of which 4 were first published ("Winter nights", "In spring", "For the leaf encountered on the highway", "What does the wind come from?"), the remaining 16 poems were previously published in other sources ("Victim", "Lights", "Autumn", "The people", "Flaming water", "Independence of conscience", "Wrestling", "A tilla beetle"*, "Oriental girl", "In great road", "White moon", "Snow again", "Binafsha", "Spinning the ridge"** , "In the arms of springs", "Land captives").

Copies of the complex are now in the Abu Rayhan Beruniy Institute of Oriental Studies (№10477), the Museum of Kokand literature (KP 1256 №103) and the Oybek House-Museum. The "Aspiration" almanac was also published by the Uzbek state publishing house in 1930, which included Chulpan's poems "ten years" and "to today's governors of Great Britain" [3. 29-30].

Nearly 140 poems by Chulpan were summed up in the four that he had ordered, as well as in various other collections published in his lifetime. These poems leave no room for the question of authorship.

Chulpan was very active in period-Time publications, regularly publishing his own publicistic articles, poems. In the press of the period – in various newspapers and magazines, more than 100 of his poems were published. It should be noted that the list that we present below is not complete. Because, firstly, Chulpan poems may have been printed-all of the time editions are not yet fully reviewed; secondly, the libraries and archives are not full of estimates of press editions: some issues are missing newspapers-magazines, some pages are missing issues too long. That is, it is unlikely that the same missing numbers or pages will have printed Chulpan's poem. Therefore, it is also inevitable that research in this direction will still continue and the list will become full and perfect. The newspaper-magazines with which Chulpan collaborated are about 60 pieces, and the geography is also quite extensive.

Chulpan contributed poems and articles to the following newspapers and magazines.

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| 1. Translator | 16. Red flag |
| 2. The Time | 17. Bukhara akhbori |
| 3. Sadoi Turkistan | 18. Young East |
| 4. Sadoi Fergana | 19. New East |
| 5. Voice of Turkestan | 20. Turkistan |
| 6. Liberty | 21. Fergana |
| 7. Salvation | 22. Darhan |
| 8. Council | 23. Red Uzbekistan |
| 9. Flag of the land | 24. Zarafshan |
| 10. Turan | 25. New Fergana |
| 11. One-day poor newspaper | 26. Eastern truth |
| 12. Great Turkistan | 27. Young lelinchi |
| 13. Workers axis | 28. Lenin spark |
| 14. Ishtirokiyun | 29. Cotton front |
| 15. RusTO | 30. Bolshevik (Organ of izboskan district) |

JOURNALS

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| 1. Oyina | 14. Maorif and teacher |
| 2. Shura | 15. Earth surface |
| 3. State | 16. New Turkistan |
| 4. Tong | 17. Young Turkistan |
| 5. Citizen fyuzat | 18. New village |
| 6. Children's world | 19. Flame |
| 7. Truth | 20. New road |
| 8. Inqilob | 21. Bright marriage |
| 9. Armug'an | 22. Sovet literature |
| 10. Mushtum | 23. Mash'ala |
| 11. Spark | 24. Gulistan |
| 12. The hearth of knowledge | 25. Literature of Uzbekistan |
| 13. Help | |

Summing up his poems in the listed sources, creating a scientific and critical text of the works of the creators of the repressive years is an inexhaustible duty of today's intellectuals.

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